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Determinants of contract duration in outsourced services in the Defense sector

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Abstract: In this paper we analyze the contract duration using Transaction Cost Theory (TCT) with a sample of 283 outsourced services in the Spanish Army during the period 2009-2014.

The analysis results show that the greater the specificity of the service, the greater the duration of the contract. In addition, it is obtained that the greater the uncertainty about the behavior of the provider, the lower the duration of the agreement. These results are consistent with existing literature and empirical works.

However, in the case of external uncertainty and incompleteness of the contract, they do not affect the contract duration. This may be because less complex services for shorter terms can be specified better and are less affected by external circumstances. Therefore, the uncertainty should be decomposed and analyzed according to their sources.

Keywords: Outsourcing, Transaction Cost Theory, Specificity, Uncertainty, Service Contracts, Defense

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1. Introduction

One of the conditions stipulated in the contracts is its duration (Crocker & Masten, 1988, Brickley et al 2006, Joskow, 2013). This is established from the needs of the contractor and supplier as well as the characteristics that accompany the given transaction (Saussier, 1999). The contract period is considered an optimization process in which there is a balance between the benefits and marginal costs of a temporary increase in the service (Crocker & Reynolds, 1993). For this reason, knowing the explanatory factors for estimating the duration of contracts it is of interest to improve efficiency in transactions.

From the Transaction Cost Theory (TCT) there are empirical studies analyzing the duration of contracts. These studies are focused on long-term contracts with a large presence of specific assets such as the transport of coal in France (Saussier, 1999), transport from coal mines (Joskow, 1987), pipelines for natural gas or franchises agreements (Crocker & Masten, 1988). Therefore, the analysis of contract duration for shorter outsourced services has great interest because they are the majority of those made and there are not researches about it.

To achieve this objective, in the following section the literature is revised and the hypotheses about the duration are set. Subsequently, in section three, we propose a model to test them, and the variables and sample used are described. Then in section four results of the estimates are shown. Finally, in the last section we explain the findings of the study.

2. Factors determining contract duration

Transaction Cost Theory (TCT) states that organizations outsource their activities outside its limits when the costs of hiring a service on the market are lower than performing them internally (Williamson, 1979). Once it is decided to outsource the service, the agreement between the parties is formalized through the "contract", which collects the requirements of economic agents involved in it (Masten & Saussier, 2000). The conditions reflected in contracts depend, inter alia, on the characteristics that present the transaction between the parties (Saussier, 1999; Crocker & Masten, 1988; Brickley et al., 2006; Joskow, 2013).

Once of these characteristics is the length of the contract, which depends on the uncertainty surrounding the transaction. In general, the greater the uncertainty

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3 surrounding the transaction, the greater the difficulty, cost and risk of establishing a
4 long-term contract because of the possibility of being trapped in an undesired situation
5 (Saussier, 1999).
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9 This uncertainty can have different sources. One of them comes from the agents'
10 behavior when one of the parties acts opportunistically hiding relevant information
11 before the contract –i.e. adverse selection- or he does not act as agreed after signing it –
12 moral hazard or hidden action- (Williamson, 1979). Opportunistic behavior may cause
13 the provider has no incentive to properly act in accordance with the instructions of the
14 contract (Brickley et al., 2006); especially if there is difficulty to verify the result of the
15 service provided (López & González, 2010).
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21 Another source of uncertainty is caused by the contract incompleteness. This
22 situation can cause that after signing the contract, the service provider neglects those
23 features that were not contained therein, in order to increase their profit (Kozhevnikova
24 & Lange, 2009). Or the supplier requires a price increase because of the difficulties to
25 carry out the service (Crocker & Reynolds, 1993). In these circumstances, the contractor
26 would have an incentive to use short-term contracts, in order to redefine the
27 characteristics of the service gradually (Kozhevnikova & Lange, 2009).
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34 Uncertainty can also be caused by the environmental instability where the
35 transaction takes place. Insecurity increases in unstable economic, social and
36 institutional environment that favors the occurrence of events beyond the control of the
37 organization (Saussier, 1999). In these cases, generally short-term contracts are
38 preferred to adjust contract terms to the environment (López & González, 2010;
39 Crocker & Masten, 1988).
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44 Based on these arguments we propose that lower the contract duration is as:

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46 **Hypothesis 1a.** The greater the uncertainty about the performance of the outsourced
47 service is.
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50 **Hypothesis 1b.** The greater the uncertainty of the environment in which the
51 transaction takes place is.
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54 **Hypothesis 1c.** The greater the uncertainty generated by the contract
55 incompleteness is.
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3 Another feature of the transaction is the degree of specificity that presents the
4 exchanged asset between the parties (Williamson, 1979). It is considered that an asset is
5 not very specific when you have many alternative uses, and therefore its value outside
6 the "contractual" relationship is approximately the same (Saussier, 1999). This feature is
7 important, because once agreed the transaction and acquired a certain degree of
8 specificity, there is incentive to act opportunistically by the contractor (e.g. refuses to
9 pay as agreed) or the provider (e.g. does not deliver the service or product on time and
10 form) according to their bargaining power, being hostage of the situation the most
11 disadvantaged one (Joskow, 1987).
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18 In these cases the contractor prefers ensure service delivery continuously, in order to
19 guarantee an adequate provider's investment (López & González, 2010), and there are
20 no losses due to lack of supply and negotiation costs with new suppliers (Joskow,
21 1987). In addition, the borrower prefers also make long-term contracts in order to
22 recover the investment made to suit customer requirements (Brickley et. al, 2006).
23 Therefore, we propose the following:
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29 **Hypothesis 2.** The greater the specificity of the assets in the transaction, the greater
30 the contract length.
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33 3. Methods and Data

34 We used a sample of service contracts signed between private firms and the Spanish
35 Army in the period 2009 to 2014. We selected a random sample of 335 contracts from
36 25 different contracting authorities within Spanish Army. For each of them, we
37 collected information from PLACES¹ (*Plataforma de contratación del Estado*): the
38 amount paid in euros (€) and the execution time expressed in days. Following other
39 authors questions, for each contract, we submitted a seven-point Likert scale
40 questionnaire² to each of the 25 contracting authorities (Vázquez, 2007; López &
41 González, 2010). We finally obtained valid information for 283 service contracts to
42 proxy the factors related to the hypothesis, and to regress the contract duration including
43 them according to the following Equation (1):
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52 [INSERT EQUATION 1]
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55 ¹ PLACE is a database where there is information about public tendering and contracts.
56 <https://contrataciondelestado.es/wps/portal/plataforma>

57 ² Before distributing the questionnaire among contracting authorities we pre-tested it with interviews from
58 experts in public procurement in the Army industry.
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3 Following prior literature about contract duration, we used several approaches to run
4 Equation 1. We performed an OLS (Ordinary Least Squares) method (Joskow, 1987;
5 Crocker & Masten, 1988; Saussier, 1999; Vázquez, 2007), and BRN (binomial negative
6 regressions) (Lin & Yan, 2016). Tables 1 and 2 show the main descriptive statistics and
7 the correlation matrix of the variables in Eq.1.
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11 [INSERT TABLES 1 & 2]
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14 4. Empirical Results 15

16 Table 3 shows the results from our regressions, where the two first columns show
17 the results from OLS regressions (without controlling (1) and controlling (2) for the
18 amount of the contracts, respectively). Third and fourth columns show the results from
19 Negative binomial regressions (without controlling (1) and controlling (2) for the
20 amount of the contracts, respectively).
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24 [INSERT TABLE 3]
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27 All the models overcome the specification tests. Also, we obtain empirical evidence
28 about the significance of the variables “*Behav.Uncert.*” (Hypothesis 1a) and
29 “*Specificity*” (Hypothesis 2). Besides, in all of them the coefficients of these variables
30 reached the expected sign. However the other sources of uncertainty,
31 “*Contract.Uncert.*” (Hypothesis 1.b) and “*Exter.Uncert.*” (Hypothesis 1.c), are not
32 significant. Besides, the control variable “amount of the contract” has an influence on
33 the contract duration since it is significant and positive without modifying the sign and
34 significance of the rest of variables. The constant term is also positive and significant in
35 all the cases.
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43 5. Conclusions 44

45 The results show that as higher is the specificity of the service, longer is the contract
46 duration. In the same way, it is obtained that as higher is the behavioral uncertainty,
47 shorter is the contract length. These results are in line with others obtained in prior
48 literature (Joskow, 1987; Saussier, 1999; Vázquez, 2010).
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52 However, for external uncertainty and contractual uncertainty the results are not
53 consistent with those predicted by the TCT. These results seems logic because less
54 complex services for shorter terms can be specified better and are less affected by
55 external circumstances..
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Equation 1

$$Duration_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Behav.Uncert._i + \beta_2 Contract.Uncert._i + \beta_3 Exter.Uncert._i + \beta_4 Specificity_i + u_i$$

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Median	Standard Deviation	25th percentile	75th percentile	Minimum	Maximum
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Duration (days)	152.44	90	151.85	30	210	1	1050
Behavioural Uncertainty	3.01	3	1.60	2	4	1	7
Contractual Uncertainty	3.64	4	1.68	2	5	1	7
External Uncertainty	3.34	3	1.59	2	4	1	7
Specificity	5.20	6	1.88	4	7	1	7

Table 2. Correlation matrix

	Specificity	Behavioural Uncertainty	Contractual Uncertainty	External Uncertainty
Specificity	1.00			
Behavioural Uncertainty	-0.03	1.00		
Contractual Uncertainty	-0.02	0.46	1.00	
External Uncertainty	-0.11	0.28	0.35	1.00

Table 3: Contract duration regressions

	OLS (1)	OLS (2)	Negative Binomial (1)	Negative Binomial (2)
Behavioral Uncertainty (Hyp. 1a)	-11.81* (0.065)	-10.57* (0.096)	-0.088** (0.042)	-0.082* (0.058)
Contractual Uncertainty (Hyp. 1b)	5.16 (0.408)	1.94 (0.758)	0.030 (0.457)	0.015 (0.707)
External Uncertainty (Hyp. 1c)	6.83 (0.267)	6.09 (0.318)	0.065 (0.126)	0.059 (0.155)
Specificity (Hyp. 2)	11.07** (0.022)	10.15** (0.035)	0.086*** (0.009)	0.082** (0.012)
Amount of the contract	-	0.0000343** (0.01)	-	2.38e-07* (0.073)
Constant	88.84** (0.017)	97.45*** (0.009)	4.502*** (0.000)	4.52*** (0.000)
Prob>F	0.052	0.0068	-	-
R²	0.033	0.039	-	-
Prob>Chi²	-	-	0.022	0.005
Pseudo R²	-	-	0.0034	0.0049

Table note: Significant at *p<0.10; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01. The standard errors are provided in the parentheses.

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